

(44–55% males) in most species, but it was far from equality in *Macrosteles sexnotatus* (29% males), *Exitianus taeniaceps* (63% males), and *Falctoya aglauros*, and *Oliarus frontalis* (75% males each). **W**

Control of rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* with seedling root dip treatments

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An experiment conducted at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, in kharif 1976 evaluated the effectiveness of selected insecticides as root-dip treatment for controlling pests in newly transplanted rice. The trial was laid out with four insecticides – chlorpyrifos, chlorfenvinphos, dimethoate, and leptophos – at different concentrations and exposure times in a randomized design replicated four times, and

Percentage of leaves affected by thrips at 15 days after transplanting. Coimbatore, India.

Chemical concn (%)	Exposure time (h)	Leaves (%) affected ^a
<i>Chlorpyrifos 20 EC</i>		
0.02	2	14.6
0.02	4	13.9
0.02	12	13.9
0.04	2	12.1
0.4	4	9.6
<i>Chlorfenvinphos 24 EC</i>		
0.02	2	17.3
0.02	4	10.1
0.02	12	14.9
0.04	2	15.2
0.04	4	17.5
<i>Dimethoate 30 EC</i>		
0.02	2	21.5
0.02	4	7.8
0.02	12	13.1
0.04	2	12.8
0.4	4	11.2
<i>Leptophos 35 EC</i>		
0.02	2	10.4
0.02	4	13.0
0.02	12	20.2
0.4	2	17.2
0.04	4	14.9
<i>Control</i>		36.1

^aS.E. = 2.93%; C.D. = 8.64%. Average of four replications.

compared with an untreated control. The seedling roots were kept in the insecticide solutions for specified times before transplanting. Pests such as thrips, whorl maggots, and stem borers on five random plants per replication were recorded at 15,30, and 45 days after transplanting (DT).

All the insecticides significantly reduced thrip incidence at 15 DT. Chlorpyrifos at 0.04% for 4 hours was best, followed by dimethoate at 0.02% for 4 hours, and chlorfenvinphos at

0.02% for 4 hours. The whorl maggot was noticed only at 30 DT, but the incidence was low. However, the incidence was minimum in the chlorfenvinphos 0.02% treatment for 4 hours. In all treatments, stem borer incidence was less than that in the control at 30 DT, but increased by 45 DT. Although not extremely effective, seedling root dip with chlorpyrifos 0.04% or dimethoate 0.02% for 4 hours can be used to control thrips in the early transplanted crop. **W**

Ragged stunt virus disease in India and Sri Lanka

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During the International Rice Testing Program monitoring tour to South India and Sri Lanka in February 1978, rice plants with symptoms of ragged stunt virus disease—identical to those previously observed in the Philippines, Indonesia, and Thailand—were observed. Numerous TNAU breeding lines at the Paddy Breeding Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore,

India, were infected. At the Batalagoda Central Rice Breeding Station, Sri Lanka; only one plant of the variety BG 34-8 was observed to be infected. Transmission studies will be conducted by Indian and Sri Lankan scientists to confirm the reports.

Recent epidemics in Indonesia and the Philippines have brought ragged stunt to the attention of rice scientists. The presence of the disease in such widely separated geographical regions as Sri Lanka, India, the Philippines, Indonesia, and Thailand indicates that it has probably been endemic in Asia for years. **W**

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Effects of herbicides on rice seed coated with activated carbon and direct seeded

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The performance of five granular herbicides in broadcast-flooded rice was evaluated in the second crop of 1977 at the Chiayi Station. Seed of the modem indica selection, Chianung-sen-yu 13 were coated with 8 kg activated carbon/ha before broadcasting on a flooded soil at the rate of 100 kg/ha. Mixed seeds of *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Cyperus difformis* were also

sown at 3 kg/ha immediately after the rice seed were broadcast. Herbicides were applied at 6 days after seeding, when most of the rice and weeds were at the one- to two-leaf stage.

Of the five granular herbicides (see table), Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE gave the best weed control. Benzglycereth (WL29226) gave the poorest control; the others controlled weeds satisfactorily. Coating rice seeds with activated carbon did not affect the effectiveness of herbicides, but it improved their selectivity to direct-seeded rice considerably. When activated carbon was used, rice toxicity ratings were reduced by almost a third in the less selective granular herbicides terbuchlor,

Effects of herbicides on rice seed coated with activated carbon and direct seeded. Second crop, 1977, Chiayi, Taiwan.

Herbicide	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Weed control ^a		Rice toxicity ^b		Yield (t/ha) ^c	
		With carbon	Without carbon	With carbon	Without carbon	With carbon	Without carbon
Terbuchlor	0.3	1.7	1.1	5.8	8.3	5.2 ab	3.1 c
Benzglycereth (WL29226)	0.5	4.3	4.3	2.0	2.1	5.7 a	5.1 ab
Piperophos/ dimethametryn	0.5/ 0.5	1.9	1.7	3.4	5.6	5.4 ab	4.5 bc
Piperophos/ 2,4-D IPE	0.5/ 0.5	8.0	8.2	3.3	4.4	5.6 ab	5.2 ab
Perfluidone/ 2,4-D IPE	1.0/ 0.25	8.6	8.8	4.8	5.1	5.3 ab	5.5 ab
Untreated control	–	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.9 ab	4.8 ab

^a Rated at 15 days after herbicide application: 1 = no control, 10 = excellent weed control.

^b Rated at 15 days after herbicide application: 1 = no control, 10 = complete kill of rice.

^c Any two means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

piperophos/dimethametryn, and piperophos/2,4-D IPE. Herbicides with protectant gave higher yields than those without; the degree of yield increase was more pronounced in herbicides that are more toxic to rice. Without protectant, plots treated with the highly toxic terbuchlor and piperophos/dimethametryn

gave lower yields than the untreated control; the difference for terbuchlor was significant at the 0.05% level. The untreated control with carbon-coated seeds also yielded higher than that without carbon coating, suggesting that activated carbon has beneficial effects other than as a herbicide protectant.

Nitrogen application as high as 180 kg N/ha resulted in a positive yield response and improved all characters observed (effective tillers, panicle length, test weight, and flag leaf area). The uptake of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in plants increased as nitrogen level increased; uptake of all nutrients was maximum at 180 kg N/ha. The protein in grain increased with increasing nitrogen level; it ranged from 8.97 to 11.20%.

With every increase in nitrogen level, grain yield increased significantly. At 0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha levels the mean yields were 4.3, 5.5, 6.2, and 6.7 t/ha, respectively. The percentage increases in yield over the control for 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha were 28, 46, and 57, respectively. The responses per kilogram of nitrogen at 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha were 21, 16, and 14 kg of paddy grain, respectively.

Nitrogen applied through urea gave the maximum grain yield (6.3 t/ha), followed by the urea + CAN combination (6.1 t/ha) and CAN (6.0 t/ha). Although the forms of nitrogen did not produce significant differences in grain yield, urea returned a higher net profit per hectare and was most economical. **W**

Soil and crop management

Effect of levels and sources of nitrogen on Jaya

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Nitrogen fertilization, one of the most effective production inputs for rice, is expensive in Asia. To increase rice yields, not only is the optimum quantity of nitrogen important; suitable sources must also be considered. A field experiment was designed through the European Nitrogen Service program at J. N. Agricultural University, Jabalpur, M. P., India, to determine optimum and profitable doses of nitrogen supplied

through suitable sources to Jaya, a high yielding dwarf indica variety.

The soil of the experimental area was sandy clay loam, low in available nitrogen (156 kg/ha), medium in available P₂O₅ (44 kg/ha), and high in available K₂O (300 kg/ha). The soil's pH was 7.0. Four levels of nitrogen (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha) and three sources (urea, calcium ammonium nitrate [CAN], and urea as basal with CAN topdressed) were used. The nitrogen was applied in 3 split doses: 50% as basal, 25% at active tillering stage, and the remaining 25% at panicle initiation. Among the data determined were ancillary characters; nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content in plants; and protein content of the grain.

The pinch method of dibbling rice in a paste of cow dung under wet conditions in southern Kerala, India

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A peculiar system of sowing rice - dibbling seeds in a paste of cow dung under wet conditions - has long been practiced in parts of southern Kerala.

After the final puddling, the farmer levels the field with a leveling board, leaving only a minimum amount of water. The field is left that way overnight (15–18 hours) to allow the sediments to settle. The next morning the standing water is drained. Raised beds about 2 to 2.5 m wide are then made by opening small furrows 10-cm deep with spades to allow the inlet and drainage of irrigation water during crop growth. The individual beds are then leveled with a device made